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PROS: Pronunciation Drill to Revamp the Oral Reading Skill of Grade 10 Learners

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ABSTRACT

An Action Research Paper

Presented to Schools Division Research Committee (SDRC)

City Schools Division Office of Antipolo

This research aimed to investigate the effectiveness of pronunciation drills on Grade 10 learners' oral reading skills, focusing on identifying the strategies and activities that were most effective in promoting pronunciation accuracy and fluency.

This study addressed the research problems through a qualitative approach employing the action research method. It was revealed from the result of the study that most students experienced a positive impact on their oral reading skills from the pronunciation drills. Effective activities included intonation exercises, reading words/phrases with word stress focus, practicing sound combinations, and reading articles emphasizing word emphasis and unstressed syllables. Many learners expressed interest and motivation, while a few faced difficulties in oral reading. Moreover, a significant majority expressed a desire to continue the pronunciation drill for improved oral reading skills and comprehension abilities.

This study focused on Grade 10 junior high school students during the academic year 2022-2023. The study provided valuable insights into effective teaching practices that could support students' language development and academic success. By examining the impact of pronunciation drills on oral reading skills, this research contributed to our understanding of strategies that could enhance students' language proficiency.

The research was crafted in line with the results of the implementation of pronunciation drill activities to comprehensively improve the oral reading skills of the Grade 10 learners of Dalig National High School. These activities focused on word stress, sentence stress, intonation, and complex sound or sound combinations for the learners.

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